

**ME 404/ChE 411
Senior Design
YNP Lake Trout Crisis**

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Abstract

Non-native lake trout were first discovered in Yellowstone Lake in 1994. It is assumed that they were illegally introduced in the mid to late eighties. Lake trout are considered a problem in Yellowstone Lake because their voracious feeding habits are devastating to the native Cutthroat Trout. Studies have shown that since 1994 cutthroat trout populations in the lake have dropped considerably due to lake trout populations. Pressure from drought and whirling disease are adding to the decline in cutthroat population and raising the urgency of ridding the lake of Lake Trout. An interested MSU Techlink employee and some professors at MSU saw the senior engineering design classes as an excellent opportunity to look into this problem from a fresh viewpoint. As a result, four engineering students from Montana State University were given the open-ended task of coming up with new ways to deal with the crisis at hand. The students have their own creativity, knowledge, and input from many interested individuals to come up with a solution to this problem. The information within this report is a look into the ideas that the students considered as solutions and studies of the effectiveness and feasibility of each.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Yellowstone National Park has identified a crisis in Yellowstone Lake. Since at least 1994, lake trout have been consuming native Yellowstone cutthroat trout. A mature lake trout is known to consume as many as 41 cutthroats annually. This pressure on the population in addition to drought effects and whirling disease are pushing the Yellowstone cutthroat towards elimination. Steadfast efforts must be made to control lake trout populations, if not eliminate them. Presently, no efficient method for accomplishing this task has been identified. The goal is to reduce lake trout populations to a level that will no longer threaten the native cutthroats.

Any design being considered for implementation must lie within the confines of the rules set forth by YNP. The proposed solution/s must:

- Be affordable
- Be minimally invasive and not damage the surrounding ecology
- Have minimal affect on species that rely on cutthroat trout for survival
- Be effective up to 100 ft/30.5 m underwater with an acceptable margin of safety
- Not remove gravel, silt, sand or other debris from the lake
- Not cause irreversible effects to the lake environment
- Cover large areas (tens of m²) with minimal effort
- Be publicly acceptable

In addition, if a diver operated or mechanical device is to be used, the proposed device must:

- Be one man operational
- Require minimal muscle power in order to avoid diver fatigue
- Have an emergency shut-off mechanism

The above listed constraints must be strictly followed due to the complexity of the Yellowstone ecosystem and the politics intrinsic to Yellowstone National Park. Also, any solution implemented will be publicly visible and thus open to public scrutiny and comment. However, there is still plenty of freedom for innovative ideas and tactics.

Chapter 2: Background

The more that is know about Yellowstone Lake, Lake Trout, and the specific problem at hand, the easier it will be to accurately determine the efficacy of solution ideas. To help in this determination process, the following “knowns and unknowns” have been listed for reference.

2.1 Yellowstone Lake

There are several facts about Yellowstone Lake which may be referenced when determining efficacy of methods. Listed below are several of the known parameters. Also, a current list of unknowns will help to identify the scope of the problem and the relevancy of possible solutions.

Lake physical properties:

- i.) Surface area = $341\text{km}^2 = 121.24 \text{ miles}^2$
- ii.) Shoreline length = $239 \text{ km} = 148.5 \text{ miles}$
- iii.) Mean depth = $48.5 \text{ m} = 159 \text{ ft}$
- iv.) Max depth = $107\text{m} = 351 \text{ ft}$
- v.) Depth profile (Figure 2.1.1)
- vi.) pH = 7.4 never <7.0

Knowns:

- i.) Three known spawning beds that are located West Thumb
- ii.) Spawning beds located near Carrington Island in West Thumb
- iii.) Water temperature near Carrington Island is approximately 40°F in early November.
- iv.) Highest know concentration of lake trout is around Carrington Island
- v.) Effects due to thermal activity on bottom of the lake are negligible
- vi.) The park service will allow equipment to be left on lake bottom if necessary
- vii.) The wind usually blows out of the southwest
- viii.) Old thermal features may be used as spawning grounds, but this hasn't been proved
- ix.) Lake Village access closes in mid November
- x.) Gill netting typically starts in mid-May

Figure 2.1.1: Yellowstone Lake Bathymetry

2.2 Lake Trout

As might be expected, there is an overwhelming amount of research that has been conducted concerning lake trout, their habits and their habitats. Initial information gathering began by reading information provided by the project supervisors. Specifically, the literature was called “Yellowstone Lake Crisis; Confronting the Lake Trout Invasion”. [11] In addition to the provided information, numerous knowledgeable sources helped compile list of information shown below.

Fish facts:

- i) Scientific name of lake trout is *salvelinus namaycush*
- ii) Lake trout have been known to be in Yellowstone Lake since the late 80's.
- iii) Prefer depths of 10 to 60 meters, seasonally dependant
- iv) Have been found at depths of 180 meters and deeper to the surface
- v) Fishermen on Yellowstone Lake are required to kill any lake trout caught
- vi) Lake trout are part of the char family
- vii) Late Trout are native to Montana in Twin Lakes, Elk Lake, and Hudson Bay drainage.
- viii) They were introduced to Lewis Lake (32 kilometers from Yellowstone Lake) in 1890
- ix) Fish in the fry stage are positively phototactic
- x) Adult lake trout are negatively phototactic
- xi) Research suggests that they typically feed at night
- xii) They lay eggs in a random pattern over a general substrate dependant area
- xiii) They have a high fidelity to spawning zones
- xiv) A 24 lb. fish is capable of laying 15,000 eggs
- xv) Oldest recorded lake trout was 62 years of age
- xvi) The world record lake trout weighed 28.2 kg. = 62 lbs.
- xvii) Young lake trout rely on sight, not smell

Figure 2.2.1: Lake Trout

2.3 Spawning Habits

In order to fully understand how to control the lake trout population, it is very important that the spawning habits are known. Knowing how, where, and when they spawn will assist in devising attack plans for adult fish, as well as their eggs and fry.

Spawning habits/facts:

- i) In Yellowstone Lake, they typically begin spawning between the end of August and the end of September
- ii) Water temperatures at and below 10°C trigger spawning instincts
- iii) Fish go through 3 spawning stages: green, ripe, and spent
- iv) They are known to spawn between 2 and 20 meters deep
- v) They spawn in areas of gravel or rubble
- vi) Spawning beds composed 25mm-50mm (1"-2") cobble (Figure 2.3.1)
- vii) They are group spawners
- viii) They are exclusive nocturnal spawners
- ix) They spawn in areas near 10s of square meters
- x) They have been observed spawning as often as every year to as few as once every three years depending on latitude
- xi) Lake trout spawn every yearly in Yellowstone Lake
- xii) Lake Trout sperm is referred to as milt

Figure 2.3.1: Spawning ground off Carrington Island

2.4 Lake Trout Eggs

Much attention has been directed towards terminating the eggs without increasing interaction among the adult fish. Several egg properties must be known to help direct efforts in this direction. Size and integrity are of particularly importance.

Egg properties:

- i) Average lake trout egg size is 0.2135 in. (1/5th in.)
- ii) They are slightly negatively buoyant
- iii) They incubate 4-5 months depending on water temperature
- iv) Incubation period is largely temperature dependent
- v) A steady flow of oxygen is needed for proper egg development
- vi) Eggs nest in cracks between rocks for protection
- vii) They are uniformly spherical on average
- viii) Typically less than .01% survive hatching

Egg information to discover:

- i) Natural frequency
- ii) Destruction temperature
- iii) Sensitivity to UV light
- iv) Oxygen deprived time period before egg dies
- v) Sensitivity to pressure variance
- vi) Force necessary to crush an egg

Figure 2.4.1: Lake trout eggs

2.5 Developmental stages

Figure 2.5.1 shows the average amount of time that lake trout spend in each stage of development. The numbers shown are affected greatly by factors such as water temperature and latitude. Values listed are estimated to model the average lake trout in Yellowstone Lake.

Figure 2.5.1: Developmental stages of lake trout

Chapter 3: Design Alternatives

When the objective of removing lake trout from Yellowstone Lake was presented, the idea of using an underwater egg sucking vacuum was mentioned with it. The needs statement was open ended and loosely defined. In other words, the sky was the limit. That said, Table A.1 shows some promising ideas that the engineering group thought of. The table consists of ideas in the left column and the scoring criteria in the top row. Based on the idea of a golf chart, each idea is compared to others by rating them in each individual category. The rating is on a scale of one to four, one being the best. Each idea has been considered to narrow the list of ideas down to a possible solution. It is very possible that in the end it is most advantageous to use several methods at the same time, attacking essentially every developmental stage of the lake trout.

During a meeting on Oct 27th with Bob Gresswell, Al Zale, Pat Bigelow and other interested contacts our goal was discussed. In order to efficiently use our time, it was decided that the students involved should concentrate strictly on innovative ideas, not existing methods. The four resulting alternatives were chosen to coincide with the engineering curriculum and target egg or larval stages. Sections 3.1 – 3.3 consist of alternatives that were initially considered, but have been ruled out. Those ideas were ruled out because they were either currently being used by the Park Service or they lacked engineering merit that we decided to pursue. Chapter 4, sections 4.1 – 4.6, are the current focus of this project.

3.1 Gillnetting

Gillnetting has been the primary method used to removing lake trout from Yellowstone Lake since they were first discovered. Gillnetting has been favored because it allows for selective fishing and tradition has proven this method effective. Gaps in the nets can be customized in order to allow smaller fish (cutthroat trout) to swim through, resulting in the capture of the large lake trout sought after. Figure 3.1.1 illustrates how gillnetting can be used at targeted depths. The idea is to net at depths greater than where cutthroat trout concentrate. According to the Yellowstone Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences 2003 annual report [4], more than 75,000 lake trout have been removed from the lake since 1994 using this method. In 2003, only 11 cutthroat trout were killed for every 100 lake trout killed using gillnetting. The nets are typically used at depths of 50-75m. August and September are usually gillnetted the heaviest with shallow-set, large mesh gillnets. This time span is preferred due to the lake trout spawning habits and locations. As this method is still used, populations of lake trout

Figure 3.1.1: Commercial gillnetting

appear to be declining. However, the rate at which the decline is happening is slow that new methods must also be employed.

3.2 Egg Vacuum Method

When confronted with the lake trout crisis, David Weston brought the idea of designing an egg-sucking vacuum with it. This idea is somewhat practical even when considering the size of Yellowstone Lake. The availability of volunteer scuba divers makes this idea attractive. Additionally, after a teleconference with Pat Bigelow, it has been assumed that the locations of at least three spawning grounds are known. The spawning grounds are estimated to be in the order of tens of square meters in size. The basic concept is illustrated in Figure 3.2.1. Essentially, volunteer divers would dive down to the spawning beds and one diver would operate this single person operated vacuum device. The device would in theory extract eggs from the spawning bed substrate, kill the eggs, and dispose of the waste.

Figure 3.2.1: Vacuum Concept

There are some serious complications that arise with this method, most of which are related to this fact that the device is operated by divers at depths. Another complication involves designing the device to be able to reach the eggs from the uneven bed floor. In order for this idea to work, the substrate must be agitated since the eggs swell and wedge between the cobbles. This method has been ruled out because of implementation complications.

3.3 Termination by Resonance

Due to the physical make up of the spawning areas, an egg destruction method that can propagate through the cracks and crevasses is favored. Using a form of ultrasonic or acoustic sound pulse might compensate for the cobble ground to deal with. The first idea considered was eliminating the eggs by vibrating them at their natural frequency. The Tacoma Narrows Bridge tragedy is a good example of this

Figure 3.3.1: Resonance frequency destruction

technique.(Figure 3.3.1) The complications with finding the natural frequency of the eggs, as well as maintaining this frequency in open water has been noted as a complication which may impair this idea. Using ultrasonic frequencies has been considered as a method to destroy the eggs and is explored in chapter 4.

3.4 Egg/Fry Trap

Research shows that trapping of lake trout eggs and fry has been conducted to measure success of reintroduction of lake trout in the Great Lakes. Two designs have been found. One is said to be successful and the other considered unsuccessful. The method mimics the spawning grounds of lake trout and captures the eggs in a container as they are laid. It has been suggested that an artificial reef was introduced to a lake and trout congregation around the artificial reef was significantly greater than elsewhere nearby. This implies high levels of success, which is promising. Perhaps artificial reefs equipped with egg traps could be employed near or on the known spawning grounds in Yellowstone Lake. Some extreme risks are introduced if this method were to be introduced. The group considered the worst case scenario to be spooking the lake trout away from a known spawning area. Introducing artificial reef on or near existing spawning grounds might result in the trout spawning elsewhere and considering the size of Yellowstone Lake, being forced to find the new beds would be devastating. This idea appears to be promising, however the risks involved may not be worth taking. After serious consideration, this method of trap has been ruled out. Moreover, the group concluded that the eggs and fry essentially trap themselves. Studies have shown that the eggs and fry stay in spawning areas of approximately 10m² for at least five months. This results in increased potential of other methods.

3.5 Fish Toxicants

Fish toxicants also known as piscicides have been widely used to eradicate all or portions of fish communities. This allows desirable or native fish species to be reintroduced without effects from predation or competition from other undesirable fish.

Rotenone, antimycin, TFM, and Bayluscide are all fish toxicants that are deemed safe and registered for use by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Antimycin has been formulated as a bottom release compound effective at killing fish eggs, is temperature sensitive, and kills almost all zoo plankton organisms when applied. Not only will antimycin kill just the eggs, but fry, fingerlings, and green lake trout in the vicinity of application. However, Antimycin is very expensive compared to its rival chemical Rotenone. Rotenone has been used as a complete and partial reclamation chemical for killing fish species. Rotenone not only affects fish, but mammals, amphibians and insects too. Proper use and handling instruction declare the chemical toxic and therefore no person should swim in treated water. Rotenone detoxifies in two to four weeks depending on the concentration used as well as the pH, temperature, depth and turbidity of the water. Rotenone repels fish where antimycin does NOT.

TFM, (3-trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol) and Bayluscide are both selective fish toxicants considered as lampricides, meaning they are used for killing sea lampreys, a primary predator of lake trout. Their use is irrelevant for the purpose of this design project; however TFM may be effective at killing fish eggs. For further discussion on antimycin, see chapter 4, section 4.6.

Chapter 4: Description of Initial Solution

4.1 Ultrasonics

The development of ultrasonic technology started in the 1950s. Since then, many different fields have been defined and explored extensively. Resonant frequency excitation, ultrasonic cleaning, and ultrasonic processing are the three most explored fields. Resonant frequency excitation has been noted for its complexity in implementation. By the nature of the process, ultrasonic cleaning operates at power levels insufficient to destroy fish eggs. As a result of these two eliminations, ultrasonic processing is the method that will be explored. The design team considers it as promising enough to be researched and experimented with into the spring 2005 semester.

Preliminary research is as follows:

Ultrasonic processors have many uses and the range of their effectiveness is increasing all the time. They are currently used in the biotechnology, analytical chemistry, environmental testing, industrial processing, pharmaceuticals, and medical fields. Ultrasonic processing has not been used for the control of fish populations. Therefore, there is no history to write about. We will concentrate on the description of ultrasonics and how they may be used to help control the lake trout population in Yellowstone Lake.

Ultrasonics, also known as ultrasound, literally means beyond sound, or above the audible spectrum. Humans are most sensitive to sounds in the 1 to 5 kHz range. The upper and lower limits of the human hearing spectrum are 19 and 0.3 kHz, respectively. Ultrasonics then refers to sounds at frequencies above 19 kHz. The two most common ultrasonic operating frequencies are 20 kHz and 40 kHz. Ultrasonics were initially researched about 90 years ago, but weren't mass produced until the 1950s. The 1950s saw the development and refinement of piezoelectric transducers. The new piezoelectric technology greatly simplified the process of creating ultrasonic frequencies.

Ultrasonics are typically considered in one of two categories: ultrasonic baths and ultrasonic liquid processors. Ultrasonic baths are used for cleaning applications. They have already been ruled out due to the low power states inherent to their operation. On the other hand, ultrasonic processors have been designed to operate at very high powers and commercial models are available at powers of 1500W and above.

Figure 4.1.1 shows the components necessary to operate an ultrasonic processor. An ultrasonic processing system consists of a power supply, converter, optional booster, probe and the liquid to be processed.

Figure 4.1.1: Components of an ultrasonic processor

1. Current is supplied at the 50/60 Hz frequency common to electrical appliances in this country.
2. The 50/60 Hz current is then transformed into a 20 kHz signal in the “Power Supply”
3. The electrical signal then goes to the “converter” where piezoelectric actuators are used to convert the 20 kHz electrical signal to a 20 kHz mechanical vibration.
4. At this point, an optional booster can be implemented to increase the amplitude of the mechanical vibrations. Higher power units may not need boosters and the use of boosters can actually cause destruction and failure of the processor.
5. The mechanical vibration is then transferred to the probe. The probe is the only part of the processor in contact with the liquid being processed. Probes come in various shapes and sizes to help maximize the efficiency of the processor.
6. The submersed vibrating probe causes some very interesting things to happen to the liquid.

Figure 4.1.2 helps illustrate what happens to liquids during ultrasonic processing. The vibrating probe emits sound waves in the liquid. These sound waves are essentially pressure waves of alternating compression and rarefaction. The repeated compression/rarefaction process causes millions of microscopic bubbles to form and the collapse.

THE CAVITATION CYCLE

Figure 4.1.2: The cavitation cycle

This collapsing is commonly referred to as cavitation. The bubbles grow until they reach an unstable size (usually about 100 microns in diameter), then implode. The implosion causes localized temperatures to 5000°C and pressures up to 500 atmospheres. This explains why liquid temperatures increase during ultrasonic treatments. Ideally, the vibrating probe will quickly create bubbles in or near enough to the eggs, and destroy their tissues with cavitation.

4.2 Potential Problems with Ultrasonics

Lake Depth:

The energy transferred from the probe to the liquid being processed is affected by the sample volume, viscosity, probe size; and the pressure of the environment. The fact that lake trout spawn at depths from 6 to 66 feet could be a problem. Ultrasonic probes vibrate easily in open air and vibrate less freely even when immersed in a small beaker of liquid. At the depths of spawning beds, pressures are greatly increased, thus probes feel more resistance to free vibration. The higher the resistance felt by the probe, the less power is delivered to the liquid and in turn, the area affected around the probe decreases. This problem may be able to be solved by simply adding a booster to the system. Another brute force method to eliminate this problem is to increase the wattage of the system being used, which brings us to our next possible problem.

Electricity:

Diver safety while operating ultrasonic probes will be paramount. Because there will be a power supply on a boat above the spawning bed, the electricity produced will need to be delivered to the converter and probe through waterproof, underwater line. It must be proven that neither the waterproof line nor the converter/probe will malfunction causing the high voltage in the system to enter the water and affect the diver.

Treating Large Areas:

Ultrasonics is currently not a method that can cover large areas. Even from a high power 1500 W system (see Figure 4.1.3), the area affected around the probe is in the 2 or 3 cubic inch range. Areas of the lake trout spawning beds in Yellowstone Lake are known to be in the tens of square meters range. This does not rule ultrasonics out though. Ed Neeb at "Sonics" has verbally agreed to help the students test the effectiveness of ultrasonics on egg destruction and help modify existing equipment or design new equipment that could be effective over larger areas.

Ed has verbally agreed to send the students a "loaner" processing set up. The set up will most likely be in the 200 W range. Ed has offered to do some testing of his own on the fish eggs as well.

Figure 4.2.1: Commercially available 1500 Watt ultrasonic processor

4.3 Microwaves

The focus of this section is to present a brief technical definition of microwave theory. Also, the discussion will quickly walk through a couple of microwave industrial applications and how they relate to the issue at hand. Examining some of these applications will hopefully reveal whether or not the use of microwaves is worth pursuing in the future for the termination of lake trout eggs. That being said lets examine the problem once again. The objective is to use microwaves to terminate lake trout eggs. Considering this, it is safe to assume that trout eggs can be cooked or collapsed while under approximately 40°F water.

Microwaves are an electromagnetic wave propagation phenomenon. They require no material support and involve both electric and magnetic fields as functions of time. Electromagnetic radiation can be defined with Coulomb's law. The magnitude of this definition of electrostatic attraction between two charges of opposite sign is dependent upon a separation distance and the permittivity of the medium the system is in.

Microwaves, otherwise known as hyperfrequency waves, form a continuous electromagnetic spectrum. The radio-frequency bands 9, 10, and 11 constitute microwaves in a frequency range from 300MHz to 300GHz. It should be noted that the microwave domain has traditionally been divided into bands designated by letters, not numbers. (i.e. P, L, S, X, etc.) At the previously mentioned frequencies, wavelengths are often on the same order as that of circuit components.

There are a multitude of applications of microwaves. Existing methods were considered to try to simulate terminating lake trout eggs in an underwater spawning bed. As previously mentioned, it is known that when eggs are laid, they settle down into the spawning ground cobble and swell up to create a tight fit. The eggs get wedged in spawning bed cobble, which has been noted to be approximately two inches deep. Taking that into consideration, it makes sense to model this problem as a soil treatment. The most obvious difference is the propagation medium. Documentation exists on sandy wet cobble soil, but doesn't consider water in place of air as a medium between the soil and the microwave source. Figures and tables reveal that power is absorbed by both spherical seeds and the soil itself. [12] Backtracking, it is then be possible to substitute the "free space" medium, air, with water. These equations could then be evaluated to reveal the power necessary to operate the corresponding microwave under water.

Once the required power has been determined to penetrate to the egg depth, the power to terminate the eggs should be determined. To model this particular part of the problem, the topic of continuous wave interaction with cell membranes was considered. Without getting too technical, the membrane of an animal cell is a layer that is approximately ten nanometers thick with protein molecules imbedded in it. These fibrous proteins are made up of alpha Helix chains of polypeptides. The peptides are much smaller than the proteins. The peptides resonate in the microwave or hyperfrequency range. When the peptides resonate, the hydrogen bonds begin to break and the cell membrane structure collapses. This failure is similar to that exhibited in Figure 4.3.1. Perhaps microwaves are the proper method for implementing the above mentioned termination by resonation, 3.3.

Figure 4.3.1: Frequency Excited Failure

With these considerations, there is a good chance it is possible to model egg destruction with a compilation of existing microwave applications. Soil treatment (substituting water for air as the medium) in conjunction with cellular membrane destruction might be a victorious combination. When considering the soil treatment alone, there was a prototype built by AUHFA that was mounted to a Renault 656 tractor. The prototype pulled 10kW of power as it successfully penetrated and sterilized seeds to a depth of 10 cm (3.94 in) at a speed of 1.5 km/hr (.93 mph). This prototype reported 80% success of seed destruction at a temperature of 8°C (46.4°F) and 100% success at 18°C (64.4°F). As a side note, a prototype by

American Company, Micrody, has been built for road repair. This device uses 100kW microwaves at a frequency of 2.45GHz with a power draw of 1.2MW to change the temperature of asphalt by up to 77°C (170.6°F). [12] The temperature change created is enough to heat asphalt to the melting point in order to fill gaps and/or cracks in the road.

4.4 Polymer Technology Overview

A fully biodegradable polymer is defined as a polymer that is completely broken down into three substances. For aerobic microorganisms the final components are carbon dioxide, water and humus. For anaerobic degradation carbon dioxide, methane and humus are produced. A major obstacle in using biodegradable polymers is making sure that the polymers are completely biodegradable. This biodegradation process depends on the properties of the polymers. These properties include the chemical bonds that are associated with the different polymers and the morphology of these. It also depends on environmental factors such as: available oxygen, temperature, the microbial cells, enzymes, and the interaction that occurs between the materials and these environmental factors.

There are two different types of polymers that are described. The first type is the biosynthetic polymers such as PHBV (polyhydroxybutyrate-polyhydroxyvalerate), which is derived from bacteria from agricultural byproducts. The second class of polymers is chemosynthetic polymers. These chemosynthetic polymers have properties that make them non biodegradable in a timely manner. An example of a chemosynthetic polymer is any poly olefin-based polymers. These polymers are not used in microorganisms' metabolism and therefore they create harmful environments for microbes. Polymers that contain aromatics are also hard for the microbes to digest and degrade. Biosynthetic polymers will be the polymers of focus for further research and discussion.

Biopolymers, also known as bioplastics can be made from naturally occurring compounds such as cellulose, starch, collagen, casein, or soy protein, to name a few. One

basic idea behind biodegradable polymers is that if they are made from compounds that are made and found in nature that nature can subsequently break them down. A polymer that is fully biodegradable, non-toxic and will degrade rapidly in water is the type of biopolymer that is needed in our application.

4.5 Industrial Applications of Polymers

The basic idea behind using a polymer gel to kill fish eggs was brought about because Lake Trout eggs need a constant flow of water to provide oxygen. It stands to reason that if a thick gel like substance could be applied over the area of a spawning bed and form a thin layer, the eggs would be suffocated and subsequently die from lack of oxygen.

Many of these polymers are used to treat dissolved sediments in water, acting by settling out unwanted sediments to the bottom of a lake or pond. Of the gels on market today, they are broken into two main categories polyelectrolytes, and aluminum coagulants.

Polyelectrolytes are water soluble macromolecule polymers that can be based on synthetic or naturally occurring chemicals and include primary coagulants and flocculant aids. Coagulants are usually positively charged (cationic) polyamines used to destabilize suspensions by allowing particles to adhere and subsequently be removed by settlement. Flocculants are polyacrylamides (PAMS), have a number of charge states, and are used to cause stabilized particles or coagulated suspensions to form aggregates that are subsequently removed by settlement or filtration in the clarification of drinking water. Non-ionic and anionic polymers are the safest and easiest to use in environmentally sensitive locations because of their low toxicity. Cationic polymers are much more toxic and toxicity increases with increasing charge density.

There are many different types of polyelectrolyte polymers, but all show a small risk to natural aquatic environments, have low mammalian toxicity and are considered innocuous. Their low level impact is NOT significant in relation to other factors that govern aquatic health. However, these polymers are a potentially significant hazard to fish incorporated by sub lethal effects and mortality by mechanical suffocation, and decreased oxygen transfer in fish gills from mucous production on the gills surface. Anionic polymers become toxic at levels greater than 1000mg/L, where cationic polymers have a much lower toxicity range. Anionic and non-ionic polymers are recognized as the safest to use and would be appropriate for environmentally sensitive locations.

Bioaccumulation does NOT occur in species exposed to polyelectrolytes because their molecular weight is too large to cross biological membranes. They are highly biodegradable where complete degradation occurs over the course of a few weeks.

Aluminum coagulants, namely aluminum sulfate (Alum), achieve significant reductions in suspended matter, nutrients, oxygen demand and turbidity. Alum and other aluminum coagulants are very stable, pose a small environmental risk, and show little toxicity threat at pH levels greater than 6.5. As pH levels drop below 6.5 the amount of dissolved aluminum ion greatly increases and is bio-available to organisms. Water treatment using aluminum coagulants increases the acidity of the water, normally no more than .5 pH units, but can be counteracted with humic substances (humic acid), calcium and dissolved organic carbon to lower the toxicity. In normal fresh waters of pH

6.5 – 8.0 it has been shown there is no increase in the amount of dissolved aluminum ion concentration, therefore fish would be minimally affected. Yellowstone Lake normally has a pH greater than 7.0, up to 7.4.

Instead fish are often affected by aluminum coagulants when the polymer accumulates on mucous gill surfaces and impairs their function. Sub-lethal and lethal effects have been shown in fish under environmental concentrations high in dissolved aluminum ions. Reports have also shown that Alum is NOT toxic to benthic organisms or crustaceans after settlement periods. Fish exposed to already high levels of dissolved aluminum may have enhanced resistance to the toxic metal as well.

Choosing a particular polymer that would be effective at killing fish eggs without causing ecological damage to the ecosystem of YNP, would be difficult where testing would definitely have to be done on several different polymers, to decide which one would be most desirable. We will be focusing on current technologies and breakthrough technologies to accurately select the appropriate polymers to test.

4.6 Antimycin

Fishery managers have been using the piscicide Antimycin A for about 35 years. Antimycin's use has changed over the years, and is only available today as Fintrol® Concentrate, currently marketed by Aquabiotics Corporation. Antimycin has been described as the most extensively studied piscicide used in fisheries, and is the most preferred fish toxicant for several situations. Antimycin is available in liquid and solid form bound to sand particle capable of diffusing at certain depths of water.

Antimycin's make up consists of four major and four minor components. Antimycin extracts are purified into a crystalline material after fermentation, and the compound is freely soluble in alcohol, but is practically insoluble in water. However, the rate of breakdown of antimycin by hydrolysis is rapid in natural waters and is accelerated by high pH, temperature, and light intensity, but is unaffected by water hardness and alkalinity. Antimycin is a stable compound, but can be destroyed rapidly by exposure to high light intensity. Complete break down occurs within one to 14 days, but usually degrades between four and seven days.

Antimycin is toxic and fatal to fish because it blocks the transfer of electrons in the mitochondria during cellular respiration in sensitive organisms. Studies have shown that antimycin is less sensitive to mammals and birds because it is rapidly absorbed into the bloodstream from the water across the gills of fish. The lethality of antimycin varies from $>1.0 \mu\text{g/L}$ to $10 \mu\text{g/L}$ over a broad spectrum of fish species, but in our case antimycin results in 100% mortality in most trout and char (Family: Salmonidae) at concentrations $>1.0 \mu\text{g/L}$. Fry and fingerling fish are more susceptible and sensitive than juvenile or adult fish, but antimycin provides rapid results and control on all post-embryonic life stages of fish. Antimycin is also effective in killing fish eggs at similar concentrations.

Furthermore, antimycin has the principle advantage over other piscicides because of its effectiveness at lower concentrations and the fish's inability to detect it. Drawbacks to using antimycin are that it neutralizes in streams with high gradients, its effectiveness decrease with increasing pH, and there are no known methods to measure antimycin concentrations in water. Currently, the existing analytical methods are only marginally capable of measuring levels likely to be required for the register of antimycin.

Unfortunately, the data on antimycin is not very extensive or comprehensive because of the limited methodology to detect the parent components and their degradation at typical treatment levels in water, restricting the successful completion of environmental fate and residue studies. As of today, the liquid form of antimycin is registered by the EPA, but the form adhered to sand forming a solid particle has not been registered, due to the lack of testing precision.

Impacts of antimycin on terrestrial wildlife, amphibians and reptiles, and invertebrates and adequate public notification and education were significant issues for those agencies using antimycin for fish control. However, existing data on antimycin does not suggest any human health concerns.

Chapter 5: Where to Go From Here

5.1: Project Future

The future of YNP lake trout crisis will restart beginning spring 2005 with two new mechanical engineering students. The new students will be given this final report and a condensed report with a brief description of the project design alternatives along with all of the design team's relevant contacts. This should be adequate to bring the new members up to speed as to where the project is and where it will be going.

A detailed economic analysis will be performed to gauge the feasibility of the proposed design alternatives. This analysis will fulfill the criteria for ChE 412 course requirements. The analysis will take into account the environmental considerations of each alternative along with the cost benefits and acceptability for use in Yellowstone National Park. An Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) or Environmental Assessment (EA) will be performed prior to any final implementation in Yellowstone Lake.

The design alternative that is chosen will be studied further and tested in the laboratory. The method that will be used to test the selected design alternative will be designed and built by the senior design team and testing will begin in the laboratory to further support the workability of the projected design. The laboratory test results should be clear and relevant, either confirming or refuting the applicability of the prospected design. The results of both the economic analysis and the laboratory tests will be used to finalize the final report. This project has a high potential of being passed on to future groups to follow up and ensure the success of this project.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

Yellowstone Lake sustains an impressive population of Yellowstone cutthroat trout. At some point in the last 25 years, non-native lake trout were illegally introduced to Yellowstone Lake. Since then, the introduced lake trout population has exploded and the cutthroat population has suffered. It is this unfortunate sequence of events that inspired David Weston to suggest this project to the engineering department at Montana State University. David's idea to assemble a group of students to research new and innovative ways of reducing the lake trout population in Yellowstone Lake was accepted by the university and the Park Service.

Fall semester 2004 marked the beginning of the group's research towards the goal of ridding Yellowstone Lake of lake trout. The design group, consisting of 2 mechanical engineering students and 2 chemical engineering students, started by amassing as much background information as possible. The project definition was redefined numerous times over this period of time. More than half way through the semester, the group decided on a specific goal and defined their direction. The goal that the group decided on was; explore new and innovative ways to control lake trout populations by concentrating on the early stages of trout development. In this statement "new and innovative ways" refers to ideas that have not been considered for this application before. Also, "early stages of trout development" consists of all trout stages in which trout are confined to spawning grounds.

Upwards of 40 different solution ideas were considered, but in the end only four were picked for development in future semesters. The four ideas that were decided on will pertain to the use of ultrasonics, microwaves, biodegradable polymers, and antimycin (chemicals). These four ideas will be explored and developed into next semester. Exploration may consist of setting up experiments, running tests, designing new equipment and documenting all results.

The final goal for this project is to present an effective idea to Yellowstone National Park and for the idea to be implemented and help decrease the lake trout population.

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Appendix A:

Table A.1 (Solution Possibilities)

Design Alternatives	Within the group's scope	Concentrates on eggs or larval stages	Effective	Affordable	Not damaging to ecology	New Innovative method	Capable of covering 10m²	TOTAL
Gill-netting	4	4	2	2	1	4	1	18
Egg sucker/vacuum	1	1	4	2	3	1	3	15
Ultrasonic destruction	1	1	---	---	---	1	---	3 - N/A
Fry trap	2	1	3	1	1	4	2	14
Microwaves	1	1	---	---	---	1	---	3 - N/A
Smother spawning beds	1	1	---	---	---	1	---	3 - N/A
Poison Lake & start over	4	1	1	4	4	4	1	19
Electro-fishing	1	4	2	2	2	4	2	17
Lake trout specific fungus	4	4	3	3	3	1	1	15
Drugs i.e. nicotine	4	4	3	4	3	1	1	20
Localized chemicals	1	1	1	2	---	4	1	10 - N/A
Depth charge	1	3	2	2	4	4	2	18
Artificial spawning bed to trap/concentrate eggs	2	1	3	2	1	4	3	16
Terminate licensing fee for anglers	4	4	2	2	2	4	1	19

APPENDIX B:

**YNP Lake Trout Crisis
Safety and Risk Management Plan**

Task	Potential Safety Hazards	Safety and Risk Mitigation Plan
1. Possible use of Ultrasonic Applications in Water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Electrical shock from 110 AC circuit b. Unknown damage to hearing c. Unintentional human cell lysing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use properly grounded tools, extension cords, etc. b. Use ear protection if necessary (more research necessary) c. Keep all body parts out of areas of ultrasonic excitation
2. Using electroshock to stun/ kill fish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. On shore electrical shock from equipment b. Accidental misuse of equipment c. Self destruction of equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Become familiar with equipment and take necessary precautions b. Perform tests with someone who has previously used equipment c. Research how equipment will perform if totally submerged in water
3. Site visit to Yellowstone National Park	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Driving on highway b. Distracting driver c. Alcohol and drugs d. Snow and ice e. Night driving f. Driving an unfamiliar vehicle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use safe driving practices b. Wear seat belt/harness c. Designated driver/abide by local and state laws d. Carry proper winter driving equipment and provisions e. Front seat passenger to help spot animals/hazards f. Familiarize self with options and test in a safe area
4. Exposure to harmful chemicals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Flammability and storage concerns b. Eye irritation / permanent damage c. Skin irritation d. Inhalation danger e. Other chemical specific hazards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Research to find chemical properties b. Obtain Safety Data Handling Sheet and follow rules b2. Use safety goggles at all times when handling c. Use rubber gloves at all times when handling if necessary d. Only use in fume hood or wide open spaces d2. Check with proper authority to make sure fume hood fully functional e. Research each chemical and note all dangers
5. Riding in boats on Yellowstone Lake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Drowning b. Falling out of boat c. Suffering hypothermia on lake in winter d. Running over unseen objects in the lake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Wear a lifejacket at all times b. Stay seated in boat if possible and grip firmly to boat while moving c. Wear sufficiently warm and waterproof clothes d. Drive boat slowly and pay attention when approaching shallows
6. Volunteer scuba diving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Drowning b. Getting the bends c. Hypothermia d. Massive fish attack e. Gear failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. All divers must be certified b. Follow typical surfacing practices to avoid such problems c. Wear proper dry suits for dives d. Don't have large chunks of bloody meat hanging off yourself e. Check all gear prior to dive